

HelioCloud Overview

Shared Open Architecture

- Instances are deployed at various institutions and are interlinked (green arrows), sharing resources.
- Open source
- Common software environments
- Data, service resources easily found & shared
- Browser-based Service Components

Network of HelioCloud Instances deployed by institution which easily share resources. Currently GSFC, APL, TOPST-Helio, CU/Boulder (May 2024)

Browser -based Service Components

High End Computing

Research Collaboration

Open Science

User Portal to create VMs in cloud (EC2)

Burstable Notebook environment which has GPU acceleration

Example: **2TB** of SDO EUV data

Open source software & tutorials at heliocloud.org

Science Gateways Demo:

We will have a heliocloud instance stood up for a hands-on demo, and are happy to talk about the tech stack.

Science Use Case: One year of SDO 94A EUV images from AIA is 129,758 files, each 14MB, totalling 1.8 TB.

*A simple irradiance for 1 year. If done **on your laptop** it would take **27 hours**.*

HelioCloud takes 25 minutes to analyze the same data

About ~ 60x faster

Data I/O faster than 8Gb/sec!

Minimal code changes (python)

...and others can repeat the same thing!